

Perceived Leadership Styles, Job Satisfaction, and Teaching Performance of the Higher Education Instructors at Occidental Mindoro State College

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Abstract:- This study aimed to find the relationship between the perceived leadership styles, job satisfaction, and teaching performance of the 48 higher education instructors at Occidental Mindoro State College. A descriptive design was used in this study. The study revealed that the respondents had a high level of perceived leadership styles – transactional and transformational. Their level of job satisfaction was high considering the school policies, supervision, and working conditions. Likewise, the respondents' level of teaching performance was very satisfactory. The results revealed that job satisfaction had a significant relationship with the leadership style and teaching performance of higher education instructors. However, there was no significant relationship between leadership style and teaching performance. None of the factors of perceived leadership styles significantly influenced the teaching performance of the respondents.

Keywords:- Perceived Leadership Styles, Job Satisfaction, Teaching Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Leadership style plays a critical role in the success of any organization or institution. It is a key driver of change and success or even a source of failure. Effective leaders can contribute to positive change and transformation of their people as well as their environment. In the context of higher education, an effective leadership style is necessary to meet the needs and challenges brought about by the sudden shift of learning modalities, diversity, and complexity of globalization (Mababu, Garcia-Revilla, Hijosa, & Moure, 2017). Further, leadership styles in education are instrumental in affecting and molding the commitment of teachers to delivering their lesson content and doing other academic-related tasks. It has a direct impact on teachers and how successful they will be able to fulfill their given responsibilities or obligations (Beri & Shu'Aibu, 2018).

Academic administrators, through effective leadership style, should ensure a working environment that is conducive to all the school's staff. In the study by Halim, Hassan, Basri, Yusof, and Ahrari (2021), the level of job satisfaction of the teachers is also affected by leadership style. If the teachers have efficient supervisors, school heads, and administrators, there is a high possibility that they can do their duties and responsibilities with quality. Thus, a profound change in education is believed to be built on effective school leadership.

Given the claims above, it is important to see how the leadership style of school heads affects the performance of the teachers in a higher education institution especially in times of the pandemic. In difficult situations, a sound decision-making process by the school leaders can boost and improve the performance of the teachers (Sarwar, Tariq, & Yong, 2022). Meanwhile, Occidental Mindoro State College (OMSC), being the only state college in the province, is also confronted with various challenges brought on by the fast-changing needs of society as well as the shift in educational schemes. To strengthen the teaching and service quality of the Institution, it is important to view the relationship between the perceived leadership style and job satisfaction of the higher education instructors. Additionally, it is critical to investigate the relationship between the leadership style and the teaching performance of the college instructors of OMSC as a basis for interventions that will aid the academe to achieve its vision and mission.

This study was guided by these research problems:

1. What is the level of perceived leadership styles of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. transactional leadership;
 - b. transformational leadership; and
 - c. passive-avoidant leadership?
2. What is the level of job satisfaction of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. school policies;
 - b. supervision; and
 - c. working conditions?

3. What is the level of teaching performance of the respondents using the Individual Evaluation in terms of:

- a. mastery of the subject matter;
- b. teaching skills;
- c. teacher-student relationship;
- d. classroom management; and
- e. personal qualities?

4. Is there a significant relationship between and among the perceived leadership styles, job satisfaction, and teaching performance of the higher education instructors at Occidental Mindoro State College?

5. Which factors of perceived leadership style significantly influence the level of teaching performance of the higher education instructors at Occidental Mindoro State College?

6. What are the issues and concerns encountered by the higher education instructors at Occidental Mindoro State College with their perceived leadership styles?

II. METHODS

➤ *Research Design*

This quantitative study utilized a descriptive research design as it tried to investigate the level of teaching performance of the college instructors in Occidental Mindoro State College as influenced by their perceived leadership style and job satisfaction. This design was used in analyzing the relationship that exists between variables and in testing whether a factor of an independent variable significantly influences the dependent variable.

➤ *Locale of the Study*

This study was conducted at Occidental Mindoro State College during the Second Semester of the Academic Year 2022-2023. Further, the Occidental Mindoro State College-Main Campus is located at Labangan Poblacion, San Jose, Occidental Mindoro.

➤ *Sample*

The researcher considered the college instructors from the College of Business Administration and Management which has the largest number of full-time and part-time instructors. Through complete enumeration, the researcher had a total of 54 respondents, however, only 48 instructors were able to respond to the survey since some of them were not available during the data-gathering procedure.

➤ *Research Instrument*

The researcher pursued to make use of research triangulation in data gathering. After the researcher read and studied relevant articles and journals, a researcher-made questionnaire was employed. More so, the instrument was tested for its reliability and validity by the experts in the field in the Institution. It has two parts wherein Part I identifies the level of the perceived leadership style of the respondents with fifteen statements. Further, Part II investigates the

respondents' level of job satisfaction with fifteen statements also. The researcher also asked the permission of the respondents in using the results of their Individual Evaluation for the Second Semester of the Academic Year 2021-2022.

Table 1. Result of reliability test.

Variables	Cronbach Alpha
Transactional Leadership	.973
Transformational Leadership	.976
Passive-Avoidant Leadership	.932
School Policies	.912
Supervision	.953
Working Conditions	.970

Table 1 shows the reliability of the researcher-made questionnaire. This test was conducted on 30 respondents from the other college at Occidental Mindoro State College. After the data was gathered, the researcher conducted a reliability test. As the results were finalized, the items with Cronbach's Alpha of .70 and above were considered.

Furthermore, to elicit more thorough responses, an interview was also conducted. Through the interview guide, the researcher was able to explore more issues and concerns encountered by the higher education instructors at Occidental Mindoro State College. Lastly, the researcher performed observation to come up with relevant insights in this study.

➤ *Data Analysis*

In analyzing the data, descriptive statistics such as weighted mean, Kendall's Tau-b, and linear regression were used for this study. Weighted mean was used to identify the level of perceived leadership style, job satisfaction, and teaching performance of the respondents. Kendall's Tau-b was used to test the relationship among the variables. To ascertain which factors of the independent variables significantly influence the dependent variable, linear regression analysis was utilized.

III. RESULTS

This section presents the results and discussions. The findings produced by the analysis of data are presented in tabular forms to provide answers to the problems of this study.

Table 2 displays the grand mean of the college instructors' perceived leadership styles which is high (mean = $2.84 \pm .319$). Both transactional and transformational leadership styles were interpreted as high. While the passive-avoidant leadership style was interpreted as low. The highest mean of $3.33 \pm .540$ is obtained by the transactional leadership.

Table 2. Respondents' level of perceived leadership styles.

Factors	Overall Mean	Std. Deviation
Transactional Leadership	3.33	.540
Transformational Leadership	3.00	.553
Passive-Avoidant Leadership	2.19	.504
Grand Mean	2.84	.319

Scale: 1.0-1.49 Very Low; 1.50-2.49 Low
2.50-3.49 High 3.5-4.00 Very High

Generally, the level of college instructors' job satisfaction is high with a grand mean of $3.25 \pm .476$. Among the factors of this variable, working conditions obtained the highest mean of $3.48 \pm .536$ which indicates that the respondents are satisfied with their working environment and co-workers.

Table 3. Respondents' level of job satisfaction.

Factors	Overall Mean	Std. Deviation
School Policies	3.11	.612
Supervision	3.16	.706
Working Conditions	3.48	.536
Grand Mean	3.25	.476

Scale: 1.0-1.49 Very Low; 1.50-2.49 Low
2.50-3.49 High 3.5-4.00 Very High

Table 4 presents the level of the respondents' teaching performance. With an overall mean of $4.35 \pm .325$, the level of teaching performance of the college instructors at Occidental Mindoro State College is very satisfactory. As data reveals, the college instructors show a very satisfactory performance as to the mastery of the subject matter (mean= $4.31 \pm .311$), teaching skills (mean= $4.34 \pm .338$), teacher-student relationship (mean= $4.36 \pm .343$), classroom management (mean= $4.33 \pm .334$), and personal qualities (mean= $4.42 \pm .330$).

Table 4. Respondents' level of teaching performance.

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mastery of the subject matter	4.31	.311
Teaching skills	4.34	.338
Teacher-student relationship	4.36	.343
Classroom management	4.33	.334
Personal qualities	4.42	.330
Overall Mean	4.35	.325

Scale: 1.00-2.49 Failed; 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory;
3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory; 4.50-5.00 Outstanding

Table 5 displays the relationships among the perceived leadership styles, job satisfaction, and teaching performance of the higher education instructors. As to the results, the leadership style has a significant relationship to job satisfaction with a p-value of .003. It was also found that job satisfaction is significantly related to teaching performance (p-value=.033).

Table 5. Relationships among the perceived leadership styles, job satisfaction, and teaching performance of the higher education instructors.

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Interpretation
Leadership Style	Job Satisfaction	.319**	.003	Significant
Leadership Style	Teaching Performance	.102	.332	Not Significant
Job Satisfaction	Teaching Performance	.222*	.033	Significant

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 summarizes the regression analysis for factors of perceived leadership style and teaching performance of the respondents. As shown, there was no significant factor among the three perceived leadership styles to the teaching performance. This implies that the level of teaching performance was not influenced by the respondents' perceived leadership style. This corroborates with the result of correlation analysis that failed to establish an extent and statistical significance (Table 5).

Table 6. Regression analysis of leadership style and the level of teaching performance of the college instructors.

Factors of Perceived Leadership Style	Dependent Variable	F	Beta Coefficient	p-value	Interpretation
Transactional	Teaching Performance	1.114	.131	.522	Not Significant
Transformational			.118	.573	Not Significant
Passive-Avoidant			-.078	.619	Not Significant

$p \leq 0.05 = \text{significant}$

IV. DISCUSSIONS

Based on the findings and results, the data reveals that the level of the respondents' perceived leadership style was high in both transactional and transformational leadership. This implies that the respondents value their supervisors discussing what is required and specifying the conditions and rewards that the employers will receive if they fulfill those requirements. The respondents also have a high level of job satisfaction and a very satisfactory overall rating for their teaching performance. This implies that instructors are skilled, dedicated, and committed to creating a positive and effective learning environment for their students.

In a nutshell, job satisfaction is significantly related to the perceived leadership style and teaching performance of the respondents. This is supported by the study of Ali and Dahie (2015) who found that leadership style had a significant and positive impact on teacher satisfaction in Secondary schools in Somalia. They had helped school administrators carry out leadership tasks and offer instructors the freedom to make their own decisions while carrying out their teaching duties in order to maintain and improve the job satisfaction of teachers at their workplace.

Moreover, the respondents presented some of the issues and concerns encountered by higher education instructors regarding their perceived leadership styles. There are three themes namely: centralized decision-making, lack of recognition, and inconsistent policies. The subthemes for each mentioned theme above were discussed below based on the perspective of the college instructors.

➤ *Centralized Decision-Making.*

Through the conduct of the interview, the researcher found that one of the concerns of the respondent is that their immediate supervisor sometimes makes decisions on their own or within a small group of trusted individuals, without seeking or considering input from others. They have the final say in all matters and maintain a significant level of control over the direction and operation of the college's program. According to Cornito (2021), the decline in creativity, innovation, and quality of education is due to the presence of centralized decision-making received in classrooms. Thus, participative decision-making is encouraged due to its vitality

for school productivity and may increase the level of the teacher's performance.

➤ *Lack of Recognition.*

To the respondents, even though giving recognition is not of the utmost importance, they do believe that it somehow affects their level of performance. They have this feeling among employees that their contributions, efforts, and achievements are not adequately acknowledged or appreciated by their supervisors. They may feel that their hard work goes unnoticed or undervalued, leading to a sense of frustration and demotivation.

➤ *Inconsistent Policies.*

Another concern of the respondents is that they are confused about some policies and guidelines due to unclear instructions from their supervisors. They struggle to understand the expectations and requirements of some academic-related tasks due to inconsistent communication or implementation of policies. The lack of clarity led to confusion, misunderstandings, and frustration among the college instructors.

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